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Policy and driver scenarios of forest biodiversity conservation and restoration in Europe

(D.2.1.1. BIOCONSENT project report with coherent scenarios for each case study)

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1. Introduction

Over the last few years, several EU environmental policies based on hard law (regulations, directives) or soft law (strategies, guidelines) have been developed. They will very likely influence forest management for the next decades to come (see Table 1). In 2019, the newly appointed EU Commission adopted a Communication on the **European Green Deal**, where forest protection in the EU is deemed a political priority in pursuing the new EU's climate and biodiversity policy objectives (55% greenhouse gas emission reduction by 2030; nature protection of 30% of the EU land area, incl. 10% under strict nature protection by 2030). The European Green Deal together with the EU Climate Law, the new EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 and the new EU Forest Strategy to 2030 call for a transformative change aiming at tackling the biodiversity and climate crisis in an integrated way. These EU policies recognise that forest ecosystems are under increasing pressure and call for action to improve the quantity and quality of the forests for the EU and its Member States to reach climate neutrality by 2050 and a healthy environment by 2030 (EC, 2019).

In the framework of the new European Green Deal Policy, the new **EU Biodiversity Strategy** to 2030, adopted in May 2020, sets out three key objectives that are to be reached until 2030: (i) to legally protect at least 30% of EU land area (an extra 4% for land as compared to today) and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network (Natura 2000); (ii) to strictly protect at least a third of the EU's protected areas representing 10% of EU land, including all remaining EU primary and old-growth forests; and to (iii) effectively manage all protected areas, defining clear conservation objectives and measures, and monitoring them appropriately. The new EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 contains a chapter on actions on forests, requiring the strict protection of all remaining EU primary and old-growth forests and increasing the forested area by planting at least three billion additional trees in line with biodiversity-friendly standards in the EU by 2030. It also aims at increasing the share of forest areas covered by management plans and developing guidelines on biodiversity-friendly practices on afforestation and closer-to-nature forestry. Furthermore, to counter the pressure of the increased demand for biomass on forests, the use of whole trees for energy production should be minimised, and bioenergy should focus primarily on wood waste and residues. An EU Nature Restoration Plan will set legally binding conservation targets to restore degraded terrestrial (forest) eco-systems, landscapes, and forest-related water bodies, to enhance sustainable management and resilience. The Plan demands measures to increase the quantity, quality and resilience of managed and protected forests in the EU-27. This refers to restoration measures such as biodiversity-friendly afforestation, reforestation and tree planting, closer-to-nature-forest management, integration of biodiversity and restoration objectives in management plans of forest owners. The Plan also aims at creating jobs, reconciling economic activities (e.g., forestry) and biodiversity objectives, and ensuring long-term productivity and value of the natural capital (EC, 2020).

As an initiative of the European Green Deal, and by building on the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Commission adopted a new **EU Forest Strategy to 2030** (EU-FES). The main objectives of the EU-FES are effective afforestation and forest preservation and restoration in Europe, to help to increase the absorption of CO₂, reduce the incidence and extent of forest fires, and promote the sustainability of forest-based bioeconomy in full respect for ecological principles favourable to biodiversity. It also aims to strictly and effectively protect all primary and old-growth forests in the EU. The EU-FES also demands that clearcutting practices in the EU countries should be approached with caution, generally avoided and used only in duly justified cases, for example when necessary for environmental or ecosystem health reasons and include environmental and ecosystem concerns (EC, 2021).

In June 2024, after a legal proposal made by the EU Commission in 2022, the EU Parliament and the Council of Member States adopted a new **EU Nature Restoration Regulation**. Among others, the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (i.) aims to restore by 2030 at least 30% and by 2050 at least 90% of all habitats (also forest habitats) in need of restoration that are protected under the EU’s **Birds and Habitats Directives** and included in the **Natura 2000** network of protected areas (Art. 4), (ii.) request EU Member States to develop National Restoration Plans taking account of national circumstances (Art. 14), plant 3 billion addition trees in full respect of ecological principles such as priority for native tree species, tree diversity, age structure diversity (Art. 13). Importantly, the EU Nature Restoration Regulation also obliges EU countries to restore biodiversity in (managed) forest ecosystems. Member States shall achieve an increasing trend at national level of a set of biodiversity indicators in (managed) forest ecosystems until 2030, and every three years thereafter, until satisfactory levels are reached. The set of indicators include (a) common forest bird index; (b) standing deadwood; (c) lying deadwood; (d) share of forest with uneven-aged structure; (e) forest connectivity; (e) stock of organic carbon; and (f) share of forests dominated by native tree species (EC 2024).

In short, the European Green Deal, the EU Habitats and Birds Directives, the new EU Nature Restoration Regulation, the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 and the EU Forest Strategy to 2030 request from the EU member states to restore and conserve forest biodiversity, increase the share of forest protected areas, effectively protect old-growth forests, increase deadwood in managed forests, and better conserve Natura 2000 forest sites. They also request countries to store more carbon in standing forests as well as to avoid clearcutting, foster close-to-nature forest management and biodiversity-friendly reforestation/afforestation in the EU-27, and beyond.

Table 1: Overview of EU biodiversity and climate policies and targets with forest relevance

EU environmental policy targets for forests	EU biodiversity and climate policies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding forest protection and restoration by protecting at least 30% of the (forest) land in the EU by 2030, of which at least 10% should be strictly protected areas of high biodiversity and climate value (e.g., forest set asides), as well as by strict protection of remaining primary and old-growth forests (currently below 5%). • Better conservation and restoration management in the EU-wide network of Natura 2000 sites (currently 50% of Natura 2000 is in forests). • Increase in the quantity, quality and resilience of managed forests and protected forests in the EU-27 by biodiversity-friendly afforestation, reforestation and tree planting, closer-to-nature-forest management, integration of biodiversity and restoration objectives in forest management plans of forest owners. • Restoration of degraded terrestrial (forest) ecosystems, landscapes, and forest-related water bodies (degradation due to climate change impacts and/or unsustainable intensive forestry practices, e.g., clear cutting, monocultures) • Sustaining biodiversity and ecosystem services while ensuring sustainable forest management. • Creating jobs, reconciling economic activities (e.g., forestry) and biodiversity objectives, and ensuring long-term productivity and value of the natural capital. 	<p>European Green Deal (Climate and Biodiversity Policy Focus)</p> <p>New EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030</p> <p>New EU Forest Strategy to 2030</p> <p>EU Birds and Habitats Directives (Natura 2000)</p> <p>EU Nature Restoration Regulation to 2030, 2040 and 2050</p>

Ambitious EU policy targets oriented towards the near or distant future (until 2030 or 2050) are important but they are not enough to secure effective implementation that would contribute to reverse the biodiversity and climate crises. Critical success factors are supportive decision-making by different (sub-) national policy-makers, enforcement agencies as well as private and public forest owners and forestry enterprises who have to implement these objectives. In turn, their behavioural responses depend on wider contextual factors such as economic demands of forest-based industries, public pressure by environmentalists, and social needs and acceptance of citizens. However, forests are characterised by very long life-cycles and are part of complex ecological and socioeconomic systems with many unknown interrelations. The complexity and uncertainty in forest development and management are further amplified by factors such as demographic changes (e.g., population growth, urbanization, aging), economic developments (e.g., market growth and decline, supply, demand, prices), policy changes (e.g., policy development and implementation, changes in governments, institutional changes), and technological developments (e.g., new products and techniques). In short, while trees grow, societal needs change over time and space. Hence, most of the future conditions and developments are yet unknown today (Sotirov et al. 2024b).

Thinking about the future and making decisions with relevance to meet future objectives is important but a challenging task. If not the only, forestry is one of the few economic activities and land use sectors that encounter very long-time horizons in production and decision making which can usually span several decades and generations (Zivnuska 1949; Price 1989). For example, forest management planning usually covers 10 years ahead, while operational and financial planning in forest- and wood-based industries is often done on a yearly and even on a daily basis. EU and national strategies and policy targets (e.g., 2030 biodiversity, climate, and bioenergy goals, 2030/2040/2050 nature restoration goals, or 2050 climate neutrality goals), including financial planning, refer to time periods between 10 to 30 years. Political and administrative turnover, and hence policy changes, take place approximately every four years (Sotirov and Memmler 2012; Sotirov et al. 2017).

As a consequence, policymakers, forest owners and other involved stakeholders have to make choices resulting in outcomes that are delayed not only by weeks, months or years, but also by decades and generations. These long-time horizons form a main source of uncertainty, which makes decision-making in forest management, planning, economy and policy a complex and contested issue (Hoogstra 2008). 15 years were reported to be the most distant horizon forest managers refer to (Hoogstra and Schanz 2009). Forest policy actors are also constrained in their ability to anticipate and shape the unknown future. While most of the future conditions and developments are yet unknown today, traditional forest policy and management approaches are usually based on past experiences and extrapolation (Hoogstra and Schanz 2008b). With progressing climate change, shifting societal demands for different forest ecosystem goods and services and coevolving transformations in policy and market framework conditions, the present and past experience do not provide complete and/or appropriate knowledge and effective strategies to anticipate the future and be prepared to meet the policy objectives (Hoogstra and Schanz 2008a; Schraml and Detten 2010; Hoogstra-Klein and Schüll 2017; Sotirov et al. 2017; Egger et al. 2024).

Achieving long term and future EU and national policy objectives remains not only a challenge in decision-making in forest policy and practice, but it can also become a “heated” forest policy controversy today (Winkel et al. 2011; Sotirov et al. 2017). Substantive cross-sectoral policy incoherence, goal conflicts and technical disputes can arise when multiple actors from several levels of governance mobilise to make decisions to realize their competing policy and management paradigms. Shaped by actors’ core values, beliefs, and interests, forest related paradigms range from ‘sustained yield’ forestry (economic primacy of timber production with minimum provision of ecosystem services) to ‘multi-purpose forestry’ (economic primacy of

timber production and provision of other ecosystem goods and services) to 'ecosystem management' (primacy of biodiversity conservation and ecological processes with minimum timber production) to 'social forestry' (primacy of local communities' social well-being with other ecosystem services and goods locally produced) to 'carbon forestry' (primacy of climate mitigation and adaptation through afforestation, reforestation and forestry) (Glück, 1994; Wiersum, 1995; Wang, 2002; Sotirov, 2010; Sotirov et al. 2024a).

To help tackle these challenges and achieve policy targets in the future through actions already today, strategic foresight methodology approaches using societal deliberation have been developed for managing and resolving uncertainties, barriers, conflicting paradigms, and conflicts in natural resource policymaking. Their main aim is to achieve transformative change through societal learning and changes in the mind-sets, values and practices of the decision-makers in policy and practice. In particular, foresight processes connect long- and short-term modes of thinking to stimulate common understanding and effective decision-making through identification and assessment of trade-offs and synergies for alternative courses of action. Foresight offers a methodology to anticipate, discuss and shape the future by connecting it with the past and present (Wollenberg et al. 2000; Swart et al. 2004; Hoogstra-Klein and Schüll 2017; Sotirov et al. 2017; Egger et al. 2024).

A key foresight methodology is the building of explorative ("what-if") future scenarios and their application to decision-making in natural resource policy and management. As shown above, forest biodiversity conservation and restoration as well as policy, economy and society are not fixed - they are evolving. Scenarios can help envisioning and shaping the future, and future images are powerful in communicating ideas and leading the way.

The remainder of this report presents first the explorative scenario analysis methodology developed and applied in the BIOCONSENT project (<https://www.bioconsent.eu/>). This inter- and trans-disciplinary research project aims to provide decision-making support for forest biodiversity conservation and restoration policy and management in Europe. A specific aim is to provide novel knowledge about trade-offs and synergies between policies, targets and management practices at the forest-biodiversity-climate-water nexus. Next, a set of 15 alternative scenario narratives (storylines) and their summary (futures tables) are provided. Altogether, this set comprises of three scenarios for each of the BIOCONSENT case studies including the EU level and four EU countries - Bulgaria, Germany, Spain and Sweden.

2. Scenario analysis methodology

Futures studies is an *academic* discipline and field of knowledge, whereas foresight is often described as *practical application* of futures investigations. *Foresight* connects the futures analyses to a decision-making situation of today, and the systematic data collection from multiple sources is often combined with participatory methods and capacity building to mobilize actions. *Strategic foresight*, also called futures research, is a transdisciplinary field of inquiry that uses a variety of methods to explore possible, plausible, and preferable futures. The main goal is to develop foresight - insight into how and why the future could be different than today - to improve policy, planning, and decision making (Amara 1981; Bell 2003; Bradfield et al. 2005; Glenn 2009). *Scenarios* are one of the most widely known techniques used in strategic foresight. They are written in compelling, accessible language, often as if the events have come to pass. Scenarios support the goal of strategic foresight by opening up for many possible and alternative futures which typically are described in terms of stories / narratives (Amara 1981; Masini 1993; van der Heijden 1996; Bell 2003; Swart 2004; Bradfield et al. 2005;

Glenn 2009; Popp and Schüll 2009; Saritas and Smith 2010; Schultz 2006; Van Vliet and Kok 2015; IPBES 2016; Hoogstra-Klein and Schül 2017).

This report develops explorative *“what-if” driver scenarios*. An explorative scenario is a plausible story about how the contextual future of a given entity of interest (in this report forest biodiversity conservation and restoration in Europe) can evolve. It includes 1) a description of an alternative end-state (a “world”) of the main influencing factors (“particular constellation of the main drivers”) in a particular timeframe (in this report in the year 2050) and 2) a logical storyline how the end-state comes about (“changes in the drivers”). Change factors (“drivers”) are factors that could change the course of events. Usually, the identification of these drivers is done through application of the STEEP analytical categories: **S**ociety, **T**echnology, **E**conomy, **E**nvironment and **P**olicy domains. Through foresight, the scenario analysis aims to explore a wide array of developments in society, technology, economy, environment, and policy that can unfold in different directions with differential impacts on the target system under study (e.g., forest biodiversity conservation and restoration in Europe). The driver scenarios will be then used to explore how actors, in this case forest owners and managers, will respond to these drivers through specific behavioral responses that are likely to be co-shaped by forest development processes (“forest management scenarios”).

Within the context of this study, scenarios are logical storylines and coherent narratives describing alternative social, economic, environmental, technological and policy developments (“conditions”) over time. The scenarios describe an end-state in the foreseeable future and how this end-state comes about through specific developments. They put emphasis on revealing what key influencing factors are driving which developments, and how the future could evolve differently based on interactions among these factors. As a basis for building these scenarios, knowledge and information on factors influencing future developments, trends, and statistical data is collected and interpreted. It is important to note that the explorative scenarios subject to this study only describe a hypothetical future and not the most likely scenarios that could materialise. In reality, some of the developments described in the scenarios could occur fully or partially, while others may not occur at all. Future realities will most likely constitute of a mixture of what the scenarios describe (Egger et al. 2024; Sotirov et al. 2024b).

Scenarios support decision making by reducing the level of uncertainty and by raising the level of knowledge. Explorative scenarios are not supposed to give predictions: the future they describe is not expected to become evidenced one day. However, trend extrapolations, predictions, projections or estimates can be included into the scenario storylines. Emphasis is on revealing different sets of basic assumptions about the key factors driving developments (“drivers”) and how the future could evolve differently based on interaction of these factors. Scenario building creates shared understanding, improves sense making about the changes ongoing and preparedness for the future. Scenarios provide a structure and language for ongoing dialogues about assumptions, emerging trends, potential surprises, diverse viewpoints, and long-term objectives and strategies. Conducting these discussions at various organizational levels and with stakeholders allows for the collection and integration of the most valuable insights from individuals with diverse backgrounds and perspectives. These insights inform on the role and potential of various drivers to create change and different outcomes. This can then be incorporated into decision-making and planning processes (Amara 1981; Masini 1993; van der Heijden 1996; Bell 2003; Robisonson 2003; Swart 2004; Bradfield et al. 2005; Glenn 2009; Popp and Schüll 2009; Kuosa 2010; Saritas and Smith 2010; Schultz 2006; Van Vliet and Kok 2015; IPBES 2016; Hoogstra-Klein and Schül 2017).

Production of alternative scenarios is based on three key principles of futures studies:

- 1) future is not predictable, there are several ways how the future can evolve, including the changes that we can imagine of taking place at some point as well as the surprises that will come unforeseen;
- 2) we can make justified assumptions about the probabilities of different events when considering the options we have, but future is not pre-determined;
- 3) our actions and choices of today affect how the future evolves.

Based on these principles, futures studies distinguish between three aspects of future development: 1.) What can or could be – *the Possible*; 2.) What is likely to be – *the Probable*; 3.) What should be – *the Preferable*. Different scenario analysis *methods and approaches* are necessary when addressing these three futures perspectives. Possible futures involve imagination and encourage creativity supported by causal systems-thinking analysis. The main method is building explorative qualitative what-if STEEP driver scenarios. Probable futures can be analysed more objectively using models based on the past and present developments. Usual techniques are forecasting scenarios, modelling projections and trend analysis. Finally, preferable futures take a normative stance (worse case vs. best case scenarios) and include also moral questions inherent in the analysis, such as, what are desired or undesired end-states, whose preferred future it is. This comes with normative scenarios, policy back-casting, road-mapping etc. (Amara 1981; Masini 1993; van der Heijden 1996; Bell 2003; Robionson 2003; Swart 2004; Bradfield et al. 2005; Glenn 2009; Popp and Schüll 2009; Kuosa 2010; Saritas and Smith 2010; Schultz 2006; Van Vliet and Kok 2015; IPBES 2016; Hoogstra-Klein and Schül 2017; Egger et al. 2024; Sotirov et al. 2024b)

For the present report's focus on exploring possible futures, explorative alternative driver scenarios were constructed. The main purpose of the scenario building process was ideation, envisioning alternative futures or alternative framework conditions, called also different "worlds" in which forest biodiversity conservation and restoration in Europe could take place in the future, specifically ca. 25 years from now (in year 2050). Accordingly, a scenario analysis method based on thinking in future alternatives ("what-if" policy and driver scenarios) was used in the present study and carried out in three interrelated methodological steps.

First, the main drivers influencing forest biodiversity conservation and restoration in Europe today and in the future were identified and allocated into Societal, Technological, Economic, Environmental and Policy (STEEP) driver categories. This was informed by a desk-based review, content analysis and synthesis of existing scientific studies and scenarios. A key resource was the comprehensive and up-to-date scientific study published under the coordination of the International Union of Forest Research Organisations - IUFRO (Egger et al. 2024; <https://www.iufro.org/de/publications/series/world-series/article/2024/03/14/world-series-vol-42-europes-wood-supply-in-disruptive-times/>). This study offers not only systematic review, individual chapters and synthesis of ecological, policy, socio-economic and technological drivers of forest management in Europe; it also offers three European level what-if scenarios of the future provision of key forest ecosystem goods and services (e.g., wood, biodiversity, carbon sequestration). These scenarios were presented to and validated by a range of public and private stakeholders representing different perspectives and issues at stake in forestry in summer 2023. Additional data sources represented a further set of national or local level (future) scenarios of forest management developed in participatory way in previous research projects such as INTEGRAL (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/282887/results>) and POLYFORES

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/606803/reporting>). Key scientific experts of the present BIOCONSENT report also co-authored the aforementioned scenario reports. Last, but not least, BIOCONSENT own scientific work on EU and national level policy analysis delivered key up-to-date information about different qualitative and/or quantitative forest-related EU policy targets for the future until 2030, 2040 and 2050 (see Table1 for some examples).

Second, alternative end-states (alternative framework conditions) at the European level were explored and summarized with the help of the futures table that arrange a coherent set of manifestations of each critical driver (Tables 2-3). For each driver, alternative thinkable future developments, called also manifestations, were explored from the data sources and creative thinking (illustrative examples in Table 2). Then, 3-5 alternative combinations of European drivers and their future manifestations that make a logical whole (A-A-A-A; B-B-B-B; C-C-C-C in Table 3) were identified and connected (illustrative examples in Table 3). The alternative end-states (set of coherent drivers and their manifestations) were described with a descriptive title, checked for consistency and described what is different between the alternative futures, how they are plausible i.e. these futures could take place. Then, three contrasting alternative end-states of drivers and manifestations at the European level were selected and for each of them a logical storyline with a sequence of events over time were drafted (driver scenarios). Purpose of this step was to illustrate that the mere “images” of future were accompanied with a compelling description how the future can evolve into a certain direction and end-state (an alternative “world”). A comparison between these European driver scenarios and the well established scenario narratives of the IPCC’s shared socio-economic pathways (O’Neil et al. 2017) helped further build coherent narratives.

Table 2: Futures table with illustrative examples on bioeconomy drivers

Driver	Driver manifestations				
Environment (different manifestations of climate change, environmental status)	slow, no dramatic changes in the environment	abrupt changes, local damages spreading to several directions	dramatic changes in certain areas, improvement of environment in others	large scale improvements in the state of the environment	Etc.
Governance (different manifestations of state vs market vs civic regulation)	global multilateral agreements, international collaboration	protectionist governments, either at national or regional level	multinational corporations ruling the game	strong citizens' movements both locally and networked across the globe	Etc.
Technology (different manifestations of internet technology and biotechnology)	internet of everything with hybrid technologies (i.e. combination of bio, nano, space technology)	biotechnology research and development stagnates (strong resistance of the new solutions)	strong biotechnology and major breakthroughs in energy and clean technologies	collapse of internet	Etc.
Economy (different manifestations of economic growth)	Stable growth distributing across the globe	strong economic fluctuations, no one single growth engine in global economy	stagnating economy in Europe, strong economic growth in Africa	stagnating economy in Europe, but strong economic growth in Arctic area	Etc.

Bio-economy (different bio-economy paradigms)	separate biomass-based sectors (forest, agri-food, fisheries) and non-renewables sectors (minerals, fossil-based...)	integrated bioeconomy based on the use of biomasses	circular economy which encompasses both renewable and non-renewable resources		Etc.
Environment (different manifestations of climate change, environmental status)	slow, no dramatic changes in the environment	abrupt changes, local damages spreading to several directions	dramatic changes in certain areas, improvement of environment in others	large scale improvements in the state of the environment	Etc.
Governance (different manifestations of state vs market vs civic regulation)	global multilateral agreements, international collaboration	protectionist governments, either at national or regional level	multinational corporations ruling the game	strong citizens' movements both locally and networked across the globe	Etc.
Technology (different manifestations of internet technology and biotechnology)	internet of everything with hybrid technologies (i.e. combination of bio, nano, space technology)	biotechnology research and development stagnates (strong resistance of the new solutions)	strong biotechnology and major breakthroughs in energy and clean technologies	collapse of internet	Etc.
Economy (different manifestations of economic growth)	Stable growth distributing across the globe	strong economic fluctuations, no one single growth engine in global economy	stagnating economy in Europe, strong economic growth in Africa	stagnating economy in Europe, but strong economic growth in Arctic area	Etc.

Table 3: Futures table with illustrative examples on bioeconomy coherent storylines

State of the environment (climate change impacts)	slow, no dramatic changes in the environment	abrupt changes, local damages spreading to several directions	dramatic changes in certain areas, improvement of environment in others	large scale improvements in the state of the environment
Governance (Policy / Society)	global agreements, international collaboration	protectionist governments, either at national or regional level	multinational corporations ruling the game	strong citizens' movements both locally and networked across the globe
Technology	Internet of Everything with hybrid technologies (i.e. combination of bio, nano, space-tech.)	biotechnology research and development stagnates (strong resistance of the new solutions)	strong biotechnology and major breakthroughs in energy and clean technologies	collapse of internet?
Economy	Stable growth distributing across the globe	strong economic fluctuations, no one single growth engine in global economy	stagnating economy in Europe, strong economic growth in Africa	stagnating economy in Europe, but strong economic growth in Arctic area
Bio-economy	separate biomass-based sectors (forest, agri-food, fisheries) and non-renewables sectors (minerals, fossil-based...)	integrated bioeconomy based on use of biomass	circular economy which encompasses both renewable and non-renewable resources	

Third, the first draft of European level scenarios with drivers, manifestations and corresponding future tables (see above) was discussed among 20 environmental and social scientists from the BIOCONSENT and LFC project at a cross-project meeting in November 2023. Using this as an input, scientists with different disciplinary backgrounds (e.g., policy, sociology, forest economy, forest ecology, forest management, etc.) brainstormed in three break out groups and further developed three sets of European explorative scenarios in a participatory and interdisciplinary approach: “Biodiversity first”, “Multifunctionality” and “Wood Economy First”. Figure 1 illustrates key results of this interdisciplinary scenario building process.

Last, but not least, using further BIOCONSENT/LFC research insights from ongoing policy analysis, forest owner surveys, and focus groups on future socio-ecological drivers of forest biodiversity restoration and forest climate adaptation, the researchers adapted the European level scenarios to explorative scenarios that are relevant at the national level in the four countries under study (Bulgaria, Germany, Spain, and Sweden) . The latter were constructed following the joint scenario building methodology described above. In consequent steps, the resulting European and national scenarios were presented to and discussed with national stakeholders in various different context. The main results of this participatory scenario analysis work will be reported in upcoming project deliverables and publications. The next sections present the main scenarios narratives and summaries at the EU and national levels.

Figure 1: European level explorative scenarios of forest biodiversity conservation and restoration (Bioconsent / LFC scenarios)

3. EU level scenarios

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Scenario narratives

Scenario 1: “Biodiversity first”

Supported by environmentally concerned, aging, stagnating, and urbanized society demanding less forest products in a context of low economic growth, the European Union and its member states are shifting toward environmental sustainability, consumption reduction, low resource and energy intensity. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Europe. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Biodiversity loss issues worldwide and in Europe remain widely unresolved. Resulting political changes in national governments and EU institutions lead to overall political priority for environmental sustainability policy targets for biodiversity conservation and restoration (e.g., in forests) as well as for biodiversity-friendly carbon sequestration in natural sinks (e.g. standing and old-growth forests). These political, socio-economic and environmental developments make forests an environmental decision making competency at the EU and national levels.

As a result, forest management in Europe is mainly governed by regulatory instruments such as EU and national level biodiversity and climate policies and strategies that prescribe, monitor and enforce environmental sustainability standards. In addition, financial compensation to cover the costs for implementing environmental standards in the forest sector are offered by EU and national subsidies. In line with the EU Biodiversity and Forest Strategies as well as the EU Nature Directives, the EU Nature Restoration Law, ambitious EU and national environmental sustainability policy targets and on-the-ground management standards for forests are formulated. They include the effective conservation of 30% of all EU forests that are located in Natura 2000 protected areas, 10% of strictly protected forests and effective protection of 100% of all primary forests. Further targets are the restoration of 84% of all degraded forest habitats in Natura 2000 sites on 100.000 km² at favourable conservation status. In the 70% remaining EU forests outside protected areas, clearcutting is banned and a close-to-nature forest management is prescribed in order to support naturally regenerated native tree species, uneven age structure, standing and lying deadwood, tree species diversity, and forest connectivity. On-the-ground standards to increase forest resilience to climate change prohibit salvage logging and prescribe biodiversity-friendly practices such as mixed uneven aged forests, natural regeneration, protected areas and forest set-asides.

Scenario 2: “Multifunctionality”

In order to respond to environmentally conscious but still consuming society demanding different services from forests, and to support economic growth within circular economy and to maintain competitive industries within its borders in a context of global rivalry with other

faster-growing world regions, the European Union and its member states are shifting toward low-carbon green economy. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Europe. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Political changes in national governments and EU institutions result in governing coalitions for multifunctional as well as environmentally-supportive policies.

These political, socio-economic, and environmental changes lead to equal policy priority at the EU level for low-carbon circular green economy, increased renewable energy self-sufficiency, environmental protection, and health and wellbeing. Triggered by this, the EU and its member states aim to achieve the overarching policy goal of the EU Green Deal and the EU LULUCF Regulation in carbon reduction by 55% until 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050 in all industry sectors, including the LULUCF sector. In particular, the EU and member states prescribe -413 Mt CO₂ per year as a specific policy target for managed forests. The EU and member states also aim at achieving the legally-binding goals of the EU Renewable Energy Directive for 45% share of renewable energy sources in the EU's overall energy mix by 2030, and beyond. To implement the EU Biodiversity Strategy, the EU Forest Strategy, and the EU Nature Restoration Law legally binding objectives, the EU and its member states also aim to protect 30% of territory for biodiversity and restore 90% of all degraded habitats, including in forests. Countries also seek to achieve the non-legally binding EU Forest Strategy priorities on environment and socio-economic values where forests and forest ecosystem services are essential for health and wellbeing, multifunctional use and socio-economic functions of forests.

As such, forest management is governed by shared responsibilities between the EU and its member states by applying a mix of regulatory and non-regulatory tools. With the aim to reconcile social, economic and environmental policy objectives, a circular and environmentally sustainable forest-based bioeconomy in Europe is incentivised through regulation and non-regulatory policy tools like knowledge, innovation, and investments. In addition, the cascading and circular use of timber by the forest-based bioeconomy sectors is prescribed by regulations. In order to contribute to climate neutrality and low-carbon circular economy, while meeting energy, biodiversity and social objectives, forest management is required to sequester carbon in natural sinks such as standing and old-growth forests, in harvested wood products, and production of bioenergy as substitute for fossil energy. To mitigate and adapt to climate change, meet timber production, forest biodiversity and social goals, a combination of forest management approaches is partly recommended partly prescribed. This includes policy actions taken to stimulate transformation of even-aged monocultures towards mixed and uneven-aged forests, large-scale reforestations and afforestations with native, exotic and genetically modified tree species, short-rotation plantations, natural forest succession and strictly protected forest areas. Economic support for these management options is provided by EU and national level subsidies and market-based payment schemes for multifunctional forests to provide multiple forest ecosystem services. In addition, market instruments for sustainable forest management and responsible forest supply chains are provided including carbon removal certification, habitat banking, eco-labelling and certification schemes.

Scenario 3: “Wood Bioeconomy First”

Due to increasing population growth, growing market competition, and unresolved security issues at the global level, the EU and its member states focus their political priorities on increasing energy, food, and biomass production to foster socio-economic development and meet growing consumption needs of economically concerned society. An expanding wood bioeconomy is seen as a way to satisfy growing needs and demands while addressing climate change. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and

deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Europe. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Political changes in national governments and EU institutions lead to political priority for wood industry-friendly and economic growth supporting policy targets. Wood imports into the EU shrink after tropical and non-tropical timber exports are redirected to faster growing and consuming world regions such as the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) countries putting pressure on EU countries to produce more domestic timber.

Due to these political, socio-economic and environmental changes, forest issues remain a key decision-making competency at the national level under the leadership of public authorities in charge of agricultural, forestry or bio-economy. Forest management is governed by a variety of national forest laws with only few common general obligations (e.g., maintenance of the forest area, restocking after harvesting or climate change damages, general guidance on sustainable forest management without further standards). EU institutions provide financial and knowledge support through the EU Rural Development Regulation, the EU Renewable Energy Directive, and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. The EU and national economic incentives, including subsidies, tax reliefs, voluntary market-driven payments, free trade on the EU common market are used to achieve forest policy targets supporting domestic wood mobilization, biomass production and supply of bio-based products.

Forest management policy targets are formulated in non-legally binding way to meet industrial needs of increased bioenergy production, growing timber-based industries, and climate mitigation by increased carbon sequestration in harvested wood products and substitution effects from wood energy. Intensive forestry operations on 85% of all forests in Europe managed mainly for timber production are supported by policy. Policy recommends clearcutting or shelter wood with planting, salvage logging, coppice forest management, even-aged forests, fast growing plantations, exotic or genetically modified drought resistant tree species. These practices are recommended to reach ambitious forest biomass policy targets for forest industries and bio-refineries. Policy also recommends to leave laying and standing deadwood and retention of habitat trees on non-economical areas and/or with low economic value.

Summary of Scenario Narratives

Table 4: Futures table for EU level policy/driver scenarios

	Policy/Driver scenarios		
Drivers	“Biodiversity First”	“Multifunctionality”	“Wood Bioeconomy First”
<i>Societal changes</i>	Environmentally concerned stagnating society with reduced consumption	Environmentally conscious high consuming stable society	Economically concerned, high consuming growing society
<i>Economic changes</i>	Low traditional economic growth with low energy and low material (biomass) consumption	Green economic growth with consumption within limits of a circular economy and environmentally sustainable materials (biomass)	High economic growth with high energy and material (biomass) consumption
<i>Policy changes</i>	Priority for nature conservation and climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level mainly governed by regulatory tools, partial support by subsidies	Priority of multi-functionality, i.e. socioeconomic benefits, nature conservation, climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level governed by both regulatory and economic tools	Priority for economic growth-related forest- and bioeconomy policy at EU and national level governed by non-regulatory voluntary, market-based tools
<i>Climate change</i>	Progressing in Europe	Progressing in Europe	Progressing in Europe

<i>Forest management prescriptions</i>	Promotion of forest biodiversity conservation/restoration and carbon forest sinks objectives	Promotion of wood, bioenergy, biodiversity, carbon and socio-economic objectives	Promotion of wood, carbon sinks in harvested wood products, and wood-based bioenergy
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4. National level scenarios: Bulgaria

Authors: Paligorov, I., Sotirov, M.

Scenario Narratives

Scenario 1: “Biodiversity first”

With the worsening state of forests during the years there is not much of a choice than to apply close-to-nature forest management and strict forest set asides. Societal expectations to adapt to drastic changes in climate and ecosystems such as forests are high. Disagreements between foresters and environmentalists over disputed territories do not turn into decades of ongoing conflicts that many had feared. It is jointly decided to give up intensive wood production and limit economic activities in public forests which still dominate country's forest ownership with their 90%. Slowed economic activity, combined with an expensive strengthening of the ecological stability of forests has led a growing number of private forest owners (10% of all ownership) to sell their forests to the public. Forest rewilding policy objectives are formulated for both public and private forests to provide more space for wildlife, wilderness and natural protection. Approved by societal acceptance, financial subsidies compensated the loss of income of the public and private forest owners (e.g. by the increase of available funding by the National Strategic Plan of Rural Development implementing the EU Rural Development Policy). As these funds had later dried, new income from payments for forest rewilding, new ways of financing biodiversity and offering non-forest services such as payments for climate-friendly forest land use and/or reducing CO₂ as well as new employment opportunities (e.g., recreation, eco-tourism) matched the lost income from timber and biomass products. Specifically, forest administrations were reformed and the dominant role of the state and municipalities was redefined.

Public support for nature protection and increase of biodiversity justified the reasoning that passive management was optimal for the ecological stability of forests. At the same time, the role of environmental factors and climate change increased. Predictions for the future showed an increase of the average annual temperature of 4 degrees as well as reduced annual rainfall. Combinations of extreme periods of drought, high temperatures, and short heavy periods of precipitation, have become more frequent. So together with a strong societal demand for nature conservation, political interests have shaped forest policy in favour of biodiversity conservation with a clear environmental policy focus. A big part of production forests have been transformed into strictly protected NATURA 2000 sites. Available funds invited a wide range of solutions and progressive ideas concerning the growing demand for nature conservation. Inspired by the success of similar projects in other countries, the government, state forest enterprises, administrators of protected areas, and NGOs have acted together and launched a new vision of creating a national forest biodiversity friendly management policy. This is supported by scientific studies indicating the influence and changes of environmental factors, e.g. an increasing trend in average annual temperatures as well as a reduction of annual rainfall. The compensation of financial losses due to nature protection restrictions on the one hand and a strong societal demand on the other hand have led to the legal enforcement of nature protection and close-to-nature forestry.

Scenario 2: “Multifunctionality”

Due to growing societal demand, forest policy objectives are formulated to support the sustainable development of forestry and the woodworking and furniture industries while seeking to deliver other forest ecosystem goods and services such as biodiversity conservation, carbon storage, and recreation. While economic demand has been relatively high and financial benefits for forest owners are provided (e.g., easy access to financial resources), the multi-purpose forestry supporting sustainability and timber production process has been costly. The income from timber production cannot be fully maximized because of some restriction of the production base and wood resources, but also because of the need to transform the wood processing industry to changing climate and hence tree species.

The public and political decision-makers show a supportive understanding of the higher costs for balanced development of forests and forestry based on sustainable timber production while caring for biodiversity, climate change, and societal needs for recreation. The larger state forest enterprises have been under economic pressure, but with institutional changes towards more powerful state enterprises and public funding they have coped with the reality. The public understands and supports the multifunctional and balanced development of forests and forestry. Some forest territories have even been left to a successive natural self-development, while the majority of forests are used more intensively for timber and other products and services. The situation is characterised by an ideological imperative to maintain or improve the current state of the forests.

Scenario 3: “Maximum wood production first”

Society has aimed to increase and maximize the potential economic yields from forests. Forestry and forest industry comprise the life and employment of nearly 20 percent of the country’s population. After stabilization of climate change impacts, in the political sphere economic forest production has won out over forest ecological sustainability. Strong economic growth has returned across Europe in general and in Bulgaria in particular. Positive economic developments in timber and biomass markets resulted in increasing incomes for public and private forest owners. Better availability of subsidies through EU and national Rural Development policies and new timber support programs for carbon reduction by harvested timber biomass and bioenergy.

The innovative use of hardwood in the construction sector has had stimulating impacts on wood based architecture and on concepts of green buildings. The generated profits from timber trade and compensation available to the forest sector notably increased the political impact and the influence of various lobbying and business groups. These strong forces lay the groundwork for economically-oriented forest policy. Thus, political advocacy strategies concerning conservation are hampered by economic interests. Due to maximum timber production, less emphasis is put on satisfying other ecosystem services (e.g., biodiversity, recreation). Societal pressures for the fulfilment of non-wood ecosystem services remain relatively low.

Summary of Scenario Narratives: Bulgaria

Table 5: Summary of scenario narratives: Bulgaria

Drivers	Policy/Driver scenarios		
	“Biodiversity First”	“Multifunctionality”	“Wood Bioeconomy First”
<i>Societal changes</i>	Environmentally sensitive public demanding nature protection and climate adaptation	Growing societal demand for multiple goods and services (wood, biodiversity, carbon, and recreation) and support for multifunctional forestry	Economically concerned, high timber commodity consuming society with low interest in non-wood products
<i>Economic changes</i>	Lower economic growth and market demand	Relatively high economic growth and market demand	Strong economic growth and market demand
<i>Policy changes</i>	Forest policy priority for nature conservation at the national level mainly governed by regulatory tool such as strictly forest protected areas, matching subsidies for income lost in line with national and EU biodiversity and rural development policies, and know-how exchange with other EU countries	Forest policy priority for multi-functionality of increased timber production, nature conservation, climate protection, etc. at the national level governed by both economic (financial subsidies, public enterprises) and regulatory (forest set asides) tools	Forest policy priority for economic growth of the forest sector at the national level governed by market tools (growing timber and biomass markets, increased incomes) and matching forestry subsidies from EU and national rural development policies and payments for carbon removals
<i>Climate change</i>	Progressing in Bulgaria (increase in annual temperature and reduction of annual rainfall)	Progressing in Bulgaria (changing climate and tree species shifts)	Progressing in Bulgaria (but with somewhat stabilization of climate change impacts)
<i>Forest management prescriptions</i>	Promotion of forest biodiversity conservation and close-to-nature forest management objectives	Promotion of more intensive wood use of the majority of forests, biodiversity conservation in some forest set asides, carbon adaptation and recreation	Maximum timber production (wood products and wood-based bioenergy), less emphasis on biodiversity and recreation

5. National level scenarios: Germany

Authors: Sotirov, M., Haase, M., Nieberg, M., Renaud, P., Sorge, S.

Scenario Narratives

Scenario 1: “Biodiversity First”

Supported by environmentally concerned, aging, stagnating, and urbanized society demanding less traditional goods and services in a context of low economic growth, Germany has shifted toward environmental sustainability, consumption reduction, low resource and energy intensity by the year 2050. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Germany, and across Europe. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting German forests. Political changes in federal and federal state governments lead to overall political priority for environmental sustainability. These political, socio-economic and environmental developments make forests an environmental decision making competency at the Federal and federal state levels in Germany, a trend noticeable for the EU level, too.

As a result, forest management in Germany is mainly governed by regulatory instruments. This includes legally binding definitions and standards for good ecological forest management practices (“gute fachliche Praxis”) replacing older terms such as proper forest management (“ordnungsgemäße Forstwirtschaft”) in the Federal and Federal states forest acts. The Federal and Federal states nature protection acts as well as national forest, biodiversity and climate strategies also support these environmental sustainability standards. In addition, financial subsidies from Federal and federal state funding sources, co-funded by the EU, offer support to forest owners for biodiverse and climate adapted forests under the condition of meeting biodiversity friendly standards as stipulated in the applicable law. In line with the EU Biodiversity and Forest Strategies, the EU Nature Directives (Natura 2000) and the EU Nature Restoration Law, national forest policy formulates environmental sustainability policy targets for on-the-ground forest management.

This includes legal obligations for effective conservation and ecological restoration of all forests in Natura 2000 sites, national parks, and other nature protected areas which altogether represent 30% of all German forests. Among this, 10% of all German forests are to be set aside as natural forests (“Wälder mit natürlicher Entwicklung”). In 70% of remaining German forests outside protected areas, a close-to-nature forest management, including continuous cover forestry and selective logging, is prescribed whereas clearcutting is banned and replanting reduced. These forests shall show substantially more naturally regenerated native tree species, uneven age structure, standing and lying deadwood, tree species diversity and forest connectivity in line with conservation biology and scientific thresholds. With the aim to increase forest resilience to climate change, the legal standards prohibit the removal of deadwood through salvage logging and prescribe biodiversity-friendly practices such as natural regeneration with native tree species, mixed uneven aged forests, protected areas and biological control of pests and diseases. Legal standards request biodiversity-friendly

carbon sequestration within standing forests, prioritizing natural sinks in standing forests over wood products as a means of carbon storage. Informational instruments such as public awareness campaigns and educational programs are used to raise awareness about the importance of conservation and restoration in supporting biodiverse and climate adapted forest ecosystems. Citizen science initiatives engage communities in monitoring and protecting local forest biodiversity conservation and restoration. Wood production is not a policy priority, but a means to achieve biodiverse and climate adapted forests.

Scenario 2: „Multifunctionality First“

In order to respond to consuming but environmentally conscious society with growing needs for multiple goods and services, and to maintain competitive industries within its borders in a context of global rivalry with other faster-growing world regions, Germany is shifting toward circular low-carbon green economy. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Germany. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Political changes in federal and federal level governments result in governing coalitions with policy priority for sustainable economy, increased renewable energy self-sufficiency, environmental protection, and health and wellbeing. Forest policy at federal and federal levels hence further supports multifunctional forest management in Germany where economic development and environmental sustainability are equally prioritized.

Aligned with EU laws, Germany seeks to contribute to carbon reduction by 55% until 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050 in all industry sectors, including the LULUCF sector. Germany also aims to contribute to achieving the legally-binding goals of the EU policy for 45% share of renewable energy sources in the EU's overall energy mix by 2030, and beyond. To implement the EU Biodiversity and Forest Strategies, and the EU Nature Directives (Natura 2000) and Nature Restoration Law, Germany aims to support forest biodiversity by an integrative approach of enhancing deadwood and active restoration in managed forests. Germany also aims to achieve national and EU non-legally-priorities on environment and socio-economic values where forests and forest ecosystem services are essential for health and wellbeing, recreation, and multifunctional use.

A combination of regulatory, fiscal, and market-based tools is applied to support forest management that maximizes the multiple values of forest resources and minimizes environmental impacts and waste. This includes a legal prescription of the cascading and circular use of timber by and for the forest-based bioeconomy. Minimum legal standards require forest management to sequester carbon in natural sinks such as standing and old-growth forests, in harvested wood products, and production of bioenergy as substitute for fossil energy. Public subsidies, market-based payment schemes and informational tools offer support for timber recycling, reuse, and remanufacturing, as well as the use of wood as a renewable and carbon-capturing construction material.

Forest policy tools encourage sustainable domestic wood supply while aiming at a transformation towards biodiverse and climate-adapted forests. This includes policy and management standards, financial means and advisory services that aim for transformation of even-aged monocultures towards mixed and uneven-aged forests, large-scale reforestations and afforestations with native, exotic and genetically modified tree species, short-rotation plantations, natural succession and strictly protected forest areas.

Scenario 3: “Wood Bioeconomy First”

Due to increasing population growth, growing market competition, and unresolved security issues at the global level, Germany focuses its political priorities on increasing energy, food, and biomass production to foster socio-economic development and meet growing consumption needs of economically concerned society. An expanding wood bioeconomy is seen as a way to satisfy growing needs and demands. Due to only partial resolution of global energy, economic development and deforestation issues, climate change is further progressing in Germany. Consequently, climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Political changes in federal and federal level governments lead to policy priority for wood industry-friendly and economic growth supporting forest policy. Wood imports into Germany shrink after tropical and non-tropical timber exports are redirected to faster growing and consuming world regions putting pressure on Germany and other EU countries to produce domestic timber. Due to these political, socio-economic and environmental changes, forest issues remain a key decision-making competency at the federal and federal state level under the leadership of public authorities in charge of agricultural, forestry or bio-economy.

Forest management is governed by a framework Federal Forest law and variety of federal state forest laws that request only few common general obligations (e.g., maintenance of the forest area, restocking after harvesting or climate change damages, general guidance on sustainable forest management without further legal standards). Instead of regulatory tools, German forest policy relies on financial incentives and market access opportunities for the forest sector, including market-based mechanisms such as carbon trading, habitat banking, and certification schemes to address environmental concerns in forest management. Government financial support for the forest-based bioeconomy stimulates industrial development and job creation along bioeconomy supply chains such as timber harvesting, wood processing, pulp and paper, bioplastics, biofuels, and biomaterials. Economic incentives, tax breaks, and investment subsidies attract private sector investment in wood bioeconomy industries. Co-funded by EU Rural Development Regulation, EU Renewable Energy Directive, and in line with EU Bioeconomy Strategy, Germany offers subsidies, tax reliefs and voluntary market-driven payments for domestic wood mobilization, biomass production and carbon storage in wood products.

Forest policy supports active forest management, including intensive forestry operations, with a priority aim to sustainably mobilize timber available in 97% of all forests in Germany managed for economic purposes; in the remaining 3% of forest protected including national parks and forest set asides, timber use restrictions apply. Forest management policy targets are formulated in non-legally binding way to meet the wood-based bioeconomy industry’s needs of increased bioenergy production, raw material supply, and climate mitigation by increased carbon sequestration in harvested wood products and substitution effects from wood energy. Germany prioritizes economic growth and resource exploitation to meet increasing demand for energy, food, and biomass products, and to maximize economic returns from forest resources while maintaining a baseline level of ecological sustainability. Hence, German policy and management recommendations favor forestry based on shorter rotation periods, clearcutting or shelter wood with planting, salvage logging, coppice forest management, even aged forests, fast-growing plantations, exotic or genetically modified drought resistant tree species while leaving laying and standing deadwood and retention of habitat trees on non-economical areas and/or with low economic value.

Table 6: Summary of scenario narratives: Germany

	Policy/Driver scenarios		
Drivers	“Biodiversity First”	“Multifunctionality”	“Wood Bioeconomy First”
<i>Societal changes</i>	Environmentally concerned stagnating society with reduced consumption	Environmentally conscious high consuming stable society	Economically concerned, high consuming growing society
<i>Economic changes</i>	Low traditional economic growth with low energy and low material (biomass) consumption	Green economic growth with consumption within limits of a circular economy and environmentally sustainable materials (biomass)	High economic growth with high energy and material (biomass) consumption
<i>Policy changes</i>	Priority for nature conservation and climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level mainly governed by regulatory tools, partial support by subsidies	Priority of multifunctionality, i.e. socioeconomic benefits, nature conservation, climate protection related forest policy at EU and national level governed by both regulatory and economic tools	Priority for economic growth-related forest- and bioeconomy policy at EU and national level governed by non-regulatory voluntary, market-based tools
<i>Climate change</i>	Progressing in Germany	Progressing in Germany	Progressing in Germany
<i>Forest management prescriptions</i>	Promotion of forest biodiversity conservation and restoration as well as carbon forest sinks objectives	Promotion of wood, bioenergy, biodiversity, carbon and socio-economic objectives	Promotion of wood, carbon sinks in harvested wood products, and wood-based bioenergy

6. National level scenarios: Spain

Authors: Pecurul, M., Aquilué, N., Hajtmarova, S.

Scenario Narratives

Scenario 1: “Biodiversity and Recreation First”

By 2050, the demand for forest protection will be high. Strong campaigning underlines the role of forests in tackling climate change and biodiversity loss. Public attitude towards forest management changes as it demands to prioritise the use of forests for leisure and biodiversity conservation. As a result, there is a paradigm shift in forest management that focuses on biodiversity-based and regulating ecosystem services. The surface of protected areas increases and reaches 30% of the territory. One-third of these are strictly protected areas (e.g., reserves). In the rest of the protected forest area, the function for social use (for example for the purpose of leisure and recreation) is prioritized. The prevailing approach to protected areas is no-touch management. The rest of the (unprotected) forest area is less regulated and has integrated close-to-nature management.

To secure the forests' ecological functions, stricter regulations are enforced in protected areas such as measures and actions for the conservation of habitats and for the restoration and conservation of hydrological river basins in application of EU Birds, Water and Habitat Directives. Forestry certification and forest management are decreasing as the expenses for the owners have increased due to the restrictions derived from new regulations. In parallel, new schemes to provide payment for ecosystem services are established. These payments reward forest owners and create new models of business that are adapted to new approaches of forest management, providing different types of social and environmental services to society (e.g.: water reservoirs, biodiversity conservation and carbon sequestration). However, at the same time, the fire risk is higher due to increasing average temperatures and more no-touch protected areas. Controlling the fire risk through active forest management or extensive agriculture might be integrated as part of new subsidy schemes. As a result, there is a rise in alternative income for rural populations.

As the rural economy is based mainly on providing services, there is certain resistance from the traditional forest sector and industry. In addition, stricter restrictions at the regulatory and practical level for timber and wood-based production present its survival challenge. Increasing taxes on wood transportation and the general application of polluter-pay mechanisms are increasing forestry costs and limiting traditional management practices. The industry faces more restrictive urban planning that limits its capability to expand its business and to grow new ones. The demand for wood products decreases by 20% over time because society prefers other competing materials.

The increasing polarization of discourses (forestry vs conservation) causes a lot of conflicts between different forest uses that are very contextualized by local conditions. In rural areas, as more people seek healthy and active lifestyles, an increased number of forests is prioritized for recreation areas. This activates the emergence of new businesses linked to tourism. In addition, new forest-related policy tools (e.g. subsidies for fire risk) can offer a new way of

income in mountain areas. However, it also increases the risk of exclusion and inequalities associated with the purchasing power of future users as there is a wave of new incomers from urban areas. This, however, can solve the current issue of rural abandonment and related wildfire risk. These social pressures result in low political support for forest management and the sector in general.

Scenario 2: Multifunctionality

The public demands more action against climate change, therefore actions for climate change mitigation and adaptation are prioritized across various sectors and industries. On one side, society demands more forests to be protected and use forests for leisure and wellbeing and on the other to consume bio-based materials and renewable energies. In forestry, this is reflected in the use of forests primarily for carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and water provision. At the same time, demand increases for the sustainable production of numerous forest products, especially mushrooms and locally produced food.

A low intensity of use enables pluralistic demands on forests. The management follows sustainable principles of close-to-nature silviculture to ensure the persistence of forests. As intensification for biomass production is perceived to be incompatible with biodiversity and recreation, forest management adapts to this challenge by lowering rotation periods and increasing energy crops. Despite the existence of forest subsidies, management costs are high and only 20 % of the cutting allowance is harvested.

There is a patchwork of policies as more forests are protected and new schemes to support and promote biomass production are put in place. The EU national rural development policies support the use of biomass as an alternative source of energy to fuel. Encouraged by this new policy frame, private/small owners are more likely to consider energy wood production, and new developments in local chains to integrate biomass. Public procurement promotes heating systems fed by biomass. Moreover, the rise in fossil fuel prices advances the growth of the biomass market. Although biomass production is part of a regional/national energy strategy, wood fuels are more important in rural areas.

The demand for both wood and non-wood products remains the same or grows moderately based on the projected GDP growth. In this growth trend, the demand in both the construction and housing sectors and all other sectors, including biomass products, will be increasing during this period, until 2050. The national and European supply of wood increases accordingly, due to the growing demand of the population for wood products as well as a greater occurrence of natural disasters. Due to the latter, there are fluctuations in timber prices (price volatility), potentially seasonal. Harvesting technology is the key to optimizing of the wood supply and making difficult-to-access forest areas accessible. This process is driven by further mechanization of harvesting technologies and results in higher safety standards.

Beyond this, new emerging industries increase the wood demand on local and regional levels. Although forest management intensification could create jobs and reactivate rural economies, no innovation is driven locally, and the industry keeps importing most of the wood from external markets and producing low-end value products (e.g.: pallets). Other forest services remain in a weaker position since there are no mechanisms to integrate them into local forest economies.

Tourism plays an increasing role in rural areas and the offer for rural temporary accommodation increases. Due to the progressive loss of primary activities, the future provision of landscape quality and other forest ecosystem values is uncertain. As the local economy stagnates, rural exodus increases which leads to more areas of forests being

undermanaged. The risk of fires increases. In general, rural and urban society is more and more detached from their environment.

These changes highlight the importance of efficient forest management and support decision systems that integrate social preferences. Since society demands more protection and leisure use, potential conflicts might arise as society opposes forest management and the market remains stagnant.

Scenario 3: Climate Mitigation and Adaptation First

As forest fires intensify due to climate change, new approaches in forest management with a focus prevailing on climate change mitigation and adaptation are demanded. The national wood supply is declining due to a political priority to keep large-diameter wood in the forest to mitigate climate change and increase biodiversity and the wood-based products offered on the regional market are imported from the European level. Products that store carbon in the long term (wood as a construction element and furniture) are particularly favoured. This greater demand for products affects the need to guarantee the availability of suitable wood for the industry, which will be diversifying its products (e.g. CLT).

Consequently, the transport radius increases, e.g. assortment for pellet production will have a radius of 200 km and other assortments will be supplied by a radius of 400-500 km. Being a scarce resource, available wood increases in price. To remain competitive, it is necessary to think about new alternative wood transport systems (e.g., trains) and harvesting technology to increase efficiency in supply and production. As a result, many local small businesses cannot keep up and close. Production is concentrated in very few competitive industries. These have the capacity to grow to compete with other large companies at a European level. However, due to increased prices, wood-based products and materials are becoming less attractive compared to fossil-based products.

To maintain industrial activity, the industry needs to invest to improve its capabilities. This entails not only increasing production but also diversifying product segments. By 2050, all of them have increased their capacity and diversified their product segments. Public-private partnerships are key to support innovation. Forest management becomes a core part of the traditional environmental organization agenda. As a result, forest management is fully integrated with activities led by NGOs focusing on biodiversity protection and linked to public incentives for on-site carbon storage.

Summary of Scenario Narratives: Spain

Table 7: Summary of scenario narratives: Spain

	Policy/Driver scenarios		
Drivers	“Biodiversity and Recreation First”	“Multifunctionality”	“Climate Mitigation and Adaptation First”
<i>Societal changes</i>	Environmentally and social wellbeing concerned society with reduced consumption of wood commodities	Environmental and social wellbeing demanding and wood commodity consuming society	Society demanding effective climate mitigation and adaptation
<i>Economic changes</i>	Low traditional (wood-based) economic growth, shifts towards new business models for water protection, biodiversity and carbon sequestration	Moderate growth in market demand for wood and non-wood products at the national level, supported by further mechanization of timber harvesting, and decline of local economy	High prices for timber products due to decline in timber supply, increased transport costs, concentration and diversification of forest industry and demise of small local businesses
<i>Policy changes</i>	Forest policy priority for nature conservation, climate protection and recreation (sub-)national and European level mainly governed by regulatory tools (protected areas regulations, recreational forest zones, water protection standards, wood taxes), partial support by payments for ecosystem services (water, biodiversity, carbon, recreation) and subsidies (fire risk)	Forest policy priority for multi-functionality, i.e. carbon sequestration, nature conservation, recreation, food as well for wood for construction and bioenergy at national level governed by both regulatory (protected areas) and economic (forestry subsidies) tools	Forest policy priority for carbon sinks in standing and old-growth forests and high quality timber products with biodiversity benefits with local timber demands covered from timber imports from EU countries; by non-regulatory voluntary, market-based tools
<i>Climate change</i>	Progressing in Spain (higher fire risks due to higher temperatures and more biomass)	Progressing in Spain (increasing fire risks)	Progressing in Spain (forest fires intensify)
<i>Forest management prescriptions</i>	Promotion of forest management for biodiversity conservation, close-to-nature forest management, water protection and recreation objectives	Promotion of forest management for biodiversity conservation, carbon storage as well as for wood for construction and bioenergy objectives	Promotion of carbon sinks in standing forests and high quality harvested wood products with biodiversity co-benefits

7. National level scenarios: Sweden

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Scenario Narratives

Scenario 1: “Biodiversity First”

The challenges of biodiversity loss and climate change have significantly influenced Sweden's environmental strategy. Efforts to combat climate change have not been sufficient and climate change is progressing. Climate related stress and disturbances, such as droughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. These developments and an intense debate about biodiversity loss have generated support for actions to promote environmental sustainability and acceptance for reducing consumption and adopting low-resource and energy-intensive practices. There is a shared understanding that profound changes in consumption patterns, alternatives to traditional economic growth, and a green circular economy are critical pathways to stay within planetary boundaries. The environmental dimension of sustainable development is prioritized, and Sweden's national political objectives include ambitious targets for addressing climate change *and* preserving biodiversity, including efforts to protect and restore forest biodiversity. Increased energy efficiency, lower energy consumption and alternative renewable energy sources have decreased the need for bioenergy feedstock from forests. The use of disposable packaging has decreased, and more efficient recycling has lowered the demand for virgin fibers for pulp and paper. The demand for bioenergy feedstock and pulpwood has therefore decreased. However, building and construction are increasingly based on wood and wood composite materials, so the demand for, and price of, timber remain high.

Sweden is committed to international agreements to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 and aims for a 55% reduction by 2030. Taxes on carbon dioxide emissions have increased drastically, all subsidies to use of fossil fuels have been removed, and legislation to prohibit fossil fuel use is underway. A significant fiscal reform has been implemented, with over 10% of tax revenues redirected to support green initiatives, thereby facilitating the transition to renewable energy sources in accordance with the EU Renewable Energy Directive's goal of a 45% share of renewables in the EU's energy mix by 2030. The ceiling for trading with emission allowances has been lowered considerably. In line with other environmentally progressive European states, Sweden has implemented EU's biodiversity and forestry strategies, the EU Nature Restoration Law, the EU Birds and Habitats Directive and the EU LULUCF regulation. Social values should in principle be protected but there are no specific mechanisms to help Indigenous Sámi reindeer herding communities or recreational interests to compete for land and forest resources.

The objective of Swedish forest policy is wood production and climate mitigation within limits set by the overarching goal to maintain and restore biodiversity. The environmental goal within the Swedish Forestry Act, which explicitly includes climate objectives, is superior to the production goal, and comprehensive ecological landscape planning is required both in the Swedish Forestry Act and the Environmental Code. The Swedish Forest Agency offers financial support for implementing ecological landscape planning across property borders.

Regulations stipulate how much forest that should be set aside for nature conservation at landscape level and there is an order of priority for which biotope types that should be set aside in different types of landscapes (e.g., late succession forest and areas with a high share of broadleaved trees). The share of productive forest that should be set aside, or managed for, nature conservation objectives (formally and voluntarily protected areas as well as retention areas and buffer zones set aside at final felling) is now over 30 % (of which at least 10% is formally protected) on a national level and in Norrbotten County. The national governmental inventory of key habitats has been re-assessed and logging of key habitats is typically prosecuted. There are regulations on leaving buffer zones close to streams, lakes and wetlands, and on preserving a certain share (15-20 %) of old forest (>120 years) in the landscape. Logging of old-growth forests is not allowed and all forests that have never been clear felled can only be managed with clearcut-free management methods. Economic incentives, like subsidies from the Forest Agency, and certification promote clearcut-free management, the restoration of biotope types that are scarce on landscape level and shifts from exotic tree species that are already planted. Practices such as stump harvesting, fertilization, the introduction of non-native tree species, and "intensive forestry" practices are prohibited, and clear-cutting should generally be avoided. Legislation regarding broadleaved trees has been strengthened, requiring at least 10% broadleaves in conifer-dominated stands, and proactive strategies to increase this proportion over time. Likewise, the regulations for preserving and restoring "fresh dead wood" in the Swedish Forestry Act, have been strengthened. FSC Certification standards have been updated and include bans on fertilization and non-native tree species (criterion 6) and the exclusion of plantations from certification (criterion 10). Sharpened requirements include landscape planning, the protection of key habitats, the adoption of clearcut-free management methods, an increase in the proportion of broadleaf trees, and the conservation of dead wood to promote uneven age structures, biodiversity, and forest continuity.

Forest owners are fully compensated for any loss of production related to nature conservation or climate mitigation measures. Subsidies and tax reductions are used to promote forest management that increases biodiversity on the landscape level and to store carbon in standing forests, forest soils and long-lived forest products.

Scenario 2: "Multifunctionality"

Faced with increasing biodiversity loss and climate change, Sweden has reconsidered its environmental and economic strategies. Efforts to combat climate change have not been sufficient and climate related stress and disturbances, such as draughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. These developments have sparked a political shift and realization that sustainable development presupposes consumption and resources use within the planet's ecological boundaries. Sweden is moving towards a circular economy combining economic competitiveness, social wellbeing, rural development, and good environmental stewardship. An aim is to diversify forest use and promote multifunctionality, i.e. ensuring that forests produce numerous goods and services, from high quality sawlogs and bioenergy feedstock to recreation and carbon storage and sequestration – while maintaining biodiversity. The ambitions regarding the environmental quality objectives on climate and biodiversity are high – but also the social values of the forest are highly valued. Reflecting a true commitment to social sustainability and multifunctional forest use, Sweden is now taking active measures to protect the rights of the Indigenous Sami people and promote Sámi culture and livelihoods. While the demand for pulp and paper has decreased, the demand for timber and bio-energy feedstock is increasing. The latter is reflected in higher prices.

Sweden is committed to international agreements to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 and the overarching policy goal of the EU Green Deal and the EU LULUCF Regulation stipulating a carbon reduction by 55% until 2030 in all industry sectors. Taxes on carbon dioxide emissions have increased drastically, all subsidies to use of fossil fuels have been removed, and legislation to prohibit fossil fuel use is underway. Over 10% of tax revenues have been redirected towards green initiatives, promoting the shift towards renewable energy in accordance with the EU Renewable Energy Directive's goal of a 45% share of renewables in the EU's energy mix by 2030. The ceiling for trading with emission allowances has been lowered considerably. Sweden is actively implementing EU's biodiversity and forestry strategies, the EU Nature Restoration Law, and the EU Birds and Habitats Directive.

The goal of Sweden's forest policy is to stimulate multiple use of the forest resource. In the Swedish Forestry Act, the overarching goal is now multifunctional forestry within the limits set by the environmental goal. Regulations have been tightened to promote quality-oriented forest management, such as extended rotation periods, shelterwood cutting, and continuous cover forestry, resulting in higher timber quality. Economic incentives (such as taxes and subsidies) and advisory services are also used to steer forest management towards production of quality timber and specifically demanded assortments, as well as alternatives to clear-cutting. Comprehensive ecological landscape planning is required both in the Swedish Forestry Act and the Environmental Code. The Swedish Forest Agency offers guidance and financial support for implementing ecological landscape planning across property borders. There are regulations on how much forest that should be set aside for nature conservation at landscape level and there is an order of priority for which biotope types that should be set aside in different types of landscapes (e.g., late succession forest and areas with a high share of broadleaved trees). The share of productive forest that should be set aside, or managed for, nature conservation objectives (formally and voluntarily protected areas as well as retention areas and buffer zones set aside at final felling) is now over 30 % (of which at least 10% is formally protected), both on national level and in Norrbotten County. The national governmental inventory of key habitats has been reimplemented and logging of key habitats is typically prosecuted. There are regulations on leaving buffer zones close to streams, lakes and wetlands, and on preserving a certain share (15-20 %) of old forest (>120 years) in the landscape. Logging of old growth-forests is not allowed, and forests that have never been clear felled, are of great importance for reindeer husbandry, or have high social values close to villages and urban areas, may only be managed with great care and clearcut-free management methods. Legislation regarding broadleaved trees has been strengthened, requiring at least 10% broadleaves in conifer-dominated stands, and proactive strategies to increase this proportion over time. Likewise, the regulations for preserving and restoring "fresh dead wood" in the Swedish Forestry Act, have been strengthened.

Despite ambitious environmental and social goals, there is a political ambition to also produce timber and biomass for the growing biobased industries. Fertilization, ditching, exotic tree species and "intensive forestry" are allowed in some areas, but with requirements for compensatory measures to maintain or increase biodiversity on the landscape level. Subsidies and tax reductions are used to promote increased production that increases both carbon sequestration and storage in the forest and long-lived forest products. The government compensates forest owners for setting aside forest and other activities that increase biodiversity on a landscape level.

The FSC Certification standard have been changed: forest owners must be able to demonstrate local benefits in the form of income and jobs; local "approval" of forestry operations near urban and settlement areas is required through consultations (Criterion 4); and multifunctionality is favored over timber production (Criterion 5). At the same time, restrictions on fertilization, ditching, exotic tree species and plantation forestry (criteria 6 and 10) have

been reduced, given that the forest owner can verify compensation measures for biodiversity. Full compensation is paid by the government to forest owners to compensate for production losses in set-asides and other measures to maintain or increase the social values, biological diversity, and carbon storage of forests.

To ensure Sami rights are respected, the status of the Reindeer husbandry Act has been strengthened in relation to the Forestry Act, and the requirements to accommodate the needs of reindeer herding have been strengthened in the Environmental Code and the FSC standard. The latter requires that FPIC (the principle of voluntary consent with knowledge of consequences) is acknowledged (explicit consent is required); that areas of special concern are managed with adapted methods which maintain or restore the grazing resource (Criterion 3); and that clear-cutting is banned in forests with pending lichens (e.g., identified in reindeer husbandry plans). To ensure that economic, ecological, and social values are maintained, specific legally required experimental zones are introduced where special management consideration is given to social values near towns and villages and in areas frequently used for recreation.

Scenario 3: “Wood and Bioeconomy First”

Faced with increasing demands of energy and other forest-based products, and urgent needs to mitigate climate change, the EU and Sweden are focusing their efforts on boosting the bioeconomy. So far, efforts to combat climate change have not been sufficient and climate related stress and disturbances, such as draughts, storms and fire are increasingly affecting forests. Therefore, forest owners as well as society in general are mostly concerned about climate change. Expected synergies between economic growth and climate mitigation is an important driver behind the current approach which aims to resolve the climate crisis through technological innovation and development. Political incentives for a fast transition to renewable energy production, substitution of fossil products and materials for wood-based, and increased European self-sufficiency of timber and biomass, have led to a significant increase in demand for wood and biomass. This development has driven up prices: timber, pulpwood, and bio energy feedstock prices are significantly higher than today. The demand for printing paper has decreased because of digitalization, but the demand for packaging material is going up as paper is replacing plastic packaging.

Sweden is committed to the EU’s goal of reducing global emissions to near-zero by 2050, although it is not legally binding. An expanding bioeconomy, increased carbon sequestration by growing forests and carbon storage in long-lived wood-based products which simultaneously can substitute fossil products are seen as the primary means to mitigate climate change – and concurrently satisfy growing human needs, generate economic growth and enhance the competitiveness of the Swedish forest industry. The aim is to create synergies between economic development, actively used and managed forests and climate adaptation. Although the EU’s mandate over forest politics is limited, national forest policy objectives are aligned with the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the Renewable Energy Directive which require Sweden to achieve a 45% share of renewable energy sources in its overall energy mix by 2030. Bioenergy feedstock from forests plays a key role in the strategy to achieve these targets. Biodiversity should in principle be maintained and social values should be protected, but no specific measures to realize these ambitions have been developed. There are no specific mechanisms to help Indigenous Sámi reindeer herding communities or recreational interests to compete for land and forest resources.

Like today, the Swedish Forestry Act is based on two equal goals, production and environment, but the latter now explicitly includes the climate. There are few policy instruments based on

regulation and economic incentives, and information and marked based certification are guiding forest management. The guiding principle is freedom with responsibility for the forest owners. The governmental regulation of the forest sector has decreased and the responsibility to fulfil the goals has in practice been handed over to the forest owners. For instance, the regulation on lowest allowable final felling age has been removed, as have the restrictions on use of exotic tree species and fertilization. The government is trying to promote forest management methods for increased production and climate adaptation through information, education and advice. Fertilization, fast-growing tree species (domestic but also exotic) and intensive forestry are promoted in some areas to increase production. Subsidies for maintaining forest roads have been introduced to facilitate higher biomass extraction.

Although the social values of forests are mentioned in political debates, they are not prioritized in legislation and certification standards. Two certification systems, FSC and PEFC, supplement legislation and now include criteria for climate-smart forest management. For instance, investments in intensive production that increases the carbon sequestration rate in the forest can be credited to forest owners. Criterion 5 has become stricter to ensure that forest owners utilize the full production potential of the forest. The criterion on nature preservation (criterion 6) has also been changed; the former restrictions on use of exotic tree species and the transformation of “natural forest” to “plantation forest” have been relaxed. The restrictions on the use of exotic tree species and fertilization on reindeer grazing lands (criterion 3) have also been removed. Forest owners are still expected to set aside key habitat areas and other areas from forest management up to the limit of 5% of their estates (criterion 6.2). Criterion 10, concerning plantation forestry, has been modified so that it is allowed to turn “natural forest” into “plantation forest” if it can be motivated for climate mitigation reasons.

Summary of Scenario Narratives: Sweden

Table 8: Summary of scenario narratives: Sweden

	Policy/Driver scenarios		
Drivers	“Environment and biodiversity”	“Multifunctionality”	“Bioeconomy and Wood”
<i>Societal changes</i>	High environmental awareness and concerns about climate change Reduced consumption	High environmental awareness and concerns about climate change and for multiple forest values Reduced/changed consumption to stay within ecological limits	Environmental concerns within economic limits and priority on climate change mitigation. Focus on the potentials of technological development Increased consumption
<i>Economic changes</i>	Changed conceptions of economic growth Green Circular economy and reduced consumption Reduced demand on/consumption of biomass (pulp and bioenergy feedstock) but high demand for timber, i.e. unchanged or higher prices on timber	Limits to growth recognized Circular economy and (reduced)/changed consumption patterns Higher demand for timber and biomass (pulp and bioenergy feedstock) due to multiple use, i.e. higher prices	Traditional economic growth desired; “Green growth” Expanding bioeconomy and increased consumption levels Higher demand on timber and biomass (pulp and bioenergy feedstock), i.e. higher prices
<i>Policy changes</i>	Stronger political regulation and economic and informational incentives;	Stronger political regulation and other incentives; EU Green	Weak regulation; freedom with responsibility; weak implementation of EU

	<p>EU conservation- and climate policy implemented (Green Deal, Forest strategy, Biodiversity Strategy, Habitats and Deforestation Directives, LULUCF Regulation)</p> <p>Priority for nature conservation AND climate mitigation/ adaptation. Wood production within ecological limits. Focus on synergies between conservation and climate mitigation and adaptation (“standing forests as stores”)</p>	<p>Deal and forest strategy implemented (Green Deal, Forest strategy, Biodiversity Strategy, Habitats and Deforestation Directives, LULUCF Regulation)</p> <p>Priority for multifunctional forest use while meeting environmental objectives and mitigating/adapting to climate change</p> <p>Focus on synergies between conservation + forest production + climate mitigation and adaptation (“standing” and “growing forests” as stores and sinks)</p>	<p>policy; EU Bioeconomy Strategy adopted.</p> <p>Priority for biomass (pulp and bioenergy feedstock) and timber production within expanding bioeconomy</p> <p>Focus on synergies between increased production of biomass and timber + substitution of fossil materials and fuels for wood, and climate mitigation (“growing forests” as sinks and wood products as stores)</p>
<i>Climate change</i>	<p>Progressing in Sweden</p> <p>Climate related stress and disturbances increasingly common and severe</p>	<p>Progressing in Sweden</p> <p>Climate related stress and disturbances increasingly common and severe</p>	<p>Progressing in Sweden</p> <p>Climate related stress and disturbances increasingly common and severe</p>
<i>Forest management</i>	<p>Stronger regulation and other economic and informational incentives to promote conservation/ restoration of forest biodiversity, ecological resilience, and ecosystem functions; and standing forests as carbon stores/sinks</p>	<p>Stronger regulation and economic- and informational incentives to promote conservation/ restoration of forest biodiversity AND a broad range of FES, including social and cultural services, timber and bioenergy feedstock; standing and growing forests as stores/sinks.</p>	<p>Weak regulation but with options and all available incentives to increase production of biomass and timber; and simultaneously boost carbon sequestration in growing forests; growing forests and sinks and wood products as stores.</p>

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